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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

D2.1 PV Waste Fragmentation

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

Eol	End of life
PV	Photovoltaic

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1. Planned criteria

A report on the mechanical processing of the PV modules will be prepared. The results of the individual processing steps will be included in this report. An evaluation of the success of the individual operations will be carried out and conclusions drawn for the planned pilot plant.

2. Mechanical Processing of End-of-life PV-Modules

2.1 Module Assessment

Solar modules from the manufacturer Kalyon were mechanically processed for the investigations as part of the Apollo project. This was done using the module type KY-395M-72F-GB, a module type with a backsheet on the back of the module (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1: SOLARMODULE KY-395M-72F-GB

The first step was to determine its composition. This involved mechanically separating the frame and junction box and determining their weights by weighing. Subsequently, by thermally treating the remaining laminate (composite of solar cells, polymers and cover glass) at 600 °C in an air atmosphere, the polymer content was determined, which results from the weight loss that occurs during combustion. In the final step, the proportions of glass, solar cells and busbars were determined by mechanical separation of the annealing residue. The determined composition shows Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: MASS BALANCE OF MODULE KY-395M-72F-GB

The main components of the module are glass, aluminium frames and plastics, which together make up 94.2 % of the total weight of the solar module. The silicon from the solar cell makes up only 3.35 % and the silver from the contacts only 0.02 %.

2.2 Mechanical Disintegration

To test the planned processing method for Eol PV modules, which is being developed as part of the Apollo project, 12 modules of the type described were processed. The first step was the mechanical separation of the frame and junction box, which was carried out manually (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3: LEFT: DISMANTLED FRAMES; RIGHT: DISMANTLED CABLES AND JUNCTION BOXES FROM KALYON PV-MODULES

In the second step, the laminates were pre-cut manually using a shearing table (Figure 4) in order to fit into the feed opening of the laboratory single-shaft shredder (Figure 5) used for further fine shredding of the laminates. If a larger shredder would be used, this pre-cutting could be omitted.

FIGURE 4: PRE-CUTTING OF PV-LAMINATES

The fine shredding in the single-shaft shredder was carried out using various screen basket inserts with different mesh sizes (40, 20 and 10 mm). Due to the limited shredding force, it was necessary to pass the material through the shredder several times while successively reducing the mesh size of the screen basket in order to achieve sufficient final fineness.

FIGURE 5: LABORATORY SINGLE-SHAFT SHREDDER

The crushed material was then screened. This resulted in the particle size distribution shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6: PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION AFTER SHREDDING OF MODULES KY-395M-72F-GB WITH 10 MM SCREEN BASKET INSERT

Crushing in the shredder resulted in a particle size distribution with maxima in the range of 2-5 mm and > 5 mm. The ignition losses of the individual fractions of the respective particle size ranges were determined (Figure 7). The fraction in the particle size range > 5 mm exhibited the highest loss on ignition, which shows that the majority of the polymers are present in this particle size range and the other fractions consist mainly of inorganic components.

FIGURE 7: DETERMINED IGNITION LOSSES OF THE SHREDDED SAMPLES

2.3 Separation of recyclable materials

The next step in the treatment process was density separation using an air separation table (Figure 8), it was used to separate the 2-5 mm and 1-2 mm fractions.

FIGURE 8: AIR SEPARATION TABLE FOR DENSITY SEPARATION

The separation using the air separation table produces two fractions (Figure 9), a light fraction containing the polymers and a heavy fraction consisting of glass and busbars (conductive strips from the solar modules made of tinned copper strip).

FIGURE 9: MATERIAL (2 -5 MM) AFTER SEPARATION USING THE AIR SEPARATION TABLE, LEFT: LIGHT FRACTION (PLASTICS); RIGHT: HEAVY FRACTION (GLASS AND BUSBARS)

Further separation of glass and busbars was planned using an eddy current separator, but this could not be carried out as its procurement was delayed. Alternatively, the separation between glass and busbars was carried out by means of density separation and separation by grain shape using sieving. This was also successful (Figure 10), but time-consuming.

FIGURE 10: SEPARATION OF GLASS AND BUSBARS BY MECHANICAL METHODS. LEFT: STARTING MATERIAL; MIDDLE: BUSBAR FRACTION; RIGHT: CLEAN GLASS FRACTION

18.3 percent by weight of the shredded PV laminates are in the grain size range of 0.1 to 2 mm. This particle size range is suitable for electrostatic separation in a corona roll separator (Figure 11). In this process, particle mixtures are separated according to their electrical conductivity, producing a conductive and a non-conductive fraction.

FIGURE 11: ELECTROSTATIC CORONA ROLL SEPARATOR FOR SEPARATING PARTICLE MIXTURES ACCORDING TO THEIR ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

The result of the separation shows Figure 12. The conductor fraction contains solar cell breakage together with busbar residues, while the non-conductor fraction contains glass together with plastic residues.

FIGURE 12: RESULT OF ELECTROSTATIC SEPARATION USING PARTICLE MIXTURES OF GRAIN SIZE 0.1 - 0.5 MM; LEFT: CONDUCTOR FRACTION (PV CELL SCRAP); RIGHT: NON-CONDUCTOR FRACTION (MIXTURE OF GLASS AND POLYMERS)

3. Conclusion

A mechanical process for the preparation of EoL PV modules was developed as part of the Apollo project. The process diagram shows Figure 13.

A total of 263 kg of solar modules were processed in the tests as part of the Apollo project. During the test trials, 33.9 kg of aluminum frames, 188 kg of glass, 26.5 kg of polymers, 1.5 kg of junction boxes, 1.4 kg of connecting cables, 3.4 kg of busbars and 9 kg of solar cell scrap were separated and recovered..

FIGURE 13: PROCESS SCHEME OF THE RECYCLING PROCESS FOR EoL-PV-MODULES

It was found that during mechanical disintegration of the solar modules in the single-shaft shredder, the splitting of the laminate mainly occurs in the area of the interface between the back contact of the solar cell and the encapsulation film. In total, only 1.4 kg of conductor fraction could be recovered by means of electrostatic separation, which corresponds to only about one ninth of the expected quantity. The reason for this lies in the unsatisfactory disintegration of the PV modules in the single-shaft shredder, as a result of which a large proportion of the silicon still remains on the polymer shreds. Higher disintegration rates are known from other types of shredder that are used in the industry to process PV modules, for example. However, such a shredder is not available at the Fraunhofer CSP.

Alternatively, however, pre-shredded PV modules could be obtained from Reiling GmbH & Co. KG, which could be further processed as part of the Apollo project.

Other options for increasing the output of cell breakage would be to chemically detach the solar cell breakage from the encapsulation film by dissolving the SiN layer (anti-reflective layer, which represents the interface between the solar cell and the film) with hydrofluoric acid. However, this method is expensive and technically demanding.

Another possibility would be a further mechanical processing stage using an impact mill, which is not available at the Fraunhofer CSP, but this would grind the silicon to dust, which would complicate the downstream processing steps.

The simplest option is thermal removal of the polymer components. This can be carried out under oxidative or inert conditions, leaving only the inorganic components behind while the polymers are degraded to carbon dioxide and water (oxidative degradation) or with the formation of pyrolysis oils and gases (operation under inert gas). However, thermal processing at the Fraunhofer CSP is only possible with very small quantities up to the kilogram scale. A partner would be required for the conversion of larger quantities of material.

